

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LAKHI****FIRST NAME: EBRAHIM****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office365 version 2409 on Windows 11

List your 6 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. What is an Academic Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7)
2. Elements of an Academic Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7–12)
3. Importance of Language (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11–13)
4. Referencing Styles (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41–42)
5. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34–39)
6. Software Aids (Mondal, Himel; Juhi, Ayesha; Dhanvijay, Anupkumar D.; Pinjar, Mohammed Jaffer; Mondal, Shaikat, n.d.)

AN INTRODUCTION TO ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

George Bernard Shaw is quoted as saying, “he who has nothing to say cannot write” (A R B Etherton 1990, 2).

Academic essays serve a particular purpose and must be well thought out. They are not to be vacuous, and the first key concept of this paper serves to introduce this purpose.

The next two concepts then provide formats, requirements and best practices when writing academic essays; as while personal creativity and discretion is often embraced; there are still certain fundamental precepts that one needs to ensure are incorporated and complied with in his essay.

Speculation is generally eschewed and essays without sources are deemed not to be credible. Accordingly, referencing forms an integral part of an essay; and the next two concepts discuss referencing styles and the bane of academic integrity: plagiarism.

The final concept introduces some software aids available to writers which if ‘wielded’ properly, may serve to benefit both writers and their ensuing readers. However, like how an improperly wielded sword turns against its own inept wielder, these tools may also yield dastardly results if misused.

2) WHAT IS AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

Academic essays are non-fictional pieces of academic work that seek to provide answers to hypotheses based on evidence, logic, and analysis (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

As their audiences are primarily from the academic community, essays should be consistent with academic expectations and should not be esoteric or vague.

One must constantly ask himself, ‘what does my reader need here?’ and to orient bits of information, explanations, and summaries briefly and gracefully, and not orient when the audience does not require it (Gordon Harvey 2009).

While there are discretions as it relates to creativity, the failure to properly present your information in a way that captures and convinces your audience will be detrimental to your essay.

3) ELEMENTS OF AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

The essential **structural** elements may be identified as the introduction, body, and conclusion (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10). These, however, should be considered as being the ‘skeleton,’ and you will be required to logically ‘flesh out’ the essay.

Harvard College has made available a brief guide to the elements of the Academic Essay (Gordon Harvey 2009).

Therein, it is provided that there are 12 terms to be familiar with when writing an academic essay, which are italicised and discussed below.

We first start with the *thesis* and *motivation*; the former of which is the main proposition of the essay and the latter of which is the reason why your essay may be appealing to its audience.

One must “study the exact meaning of each word in your topic and don’t start to find a thesis or make a plan until you are certain that you know exactly what the subject is” (Eherton 1990, 20).

The *stance* or relationship between the writer, the readers, and the subjects should also be disclosed in the essay.

The thesis should be clearly stated and remembered throughout. '*Keyterms*' then augment your thesis and are the concepts both for and against your argument.

The essay must refer to *evidence* that is being used to support the points being made and *sources* to allow for the independent confirmation of the veracity of what is being proposed. Consequentially, the *analysis* of materials presented allows the reader to understand why you have utilised certain evidence or sources, as well as the *orienting* of the same to ensure that you do not unnecessarily provide information that is superfluous or irrelevant.

While researchers collect data, they do so to support an answer to their thesis, and in so doing, 'they also imagine a community of readers who they believe will share their interest and help them test and support an answer' to the same (Turabian 2018, 20)

Providing a balanced paper is also important, as a biased perspective that is not properly disclaimed or addressed may be morally reprehensible. Hence, *reflecting* is also important to provide for potential counterarguments or views or to seek to explain, or contextualise, or disclaim what has been presented. For example, this would be the place to disclaim potential limitations in respect of sources used, which may be old and hence potentially outdated, or limited in respect of the demographic and hence potentially not representative of the entire population being referred to in your essay.

Sequencing the topics and the presentation by way of the *structure* is also of paramount importance, and your points should be presented logically, and sections should be used for multiple parts (Cleenewerck and Gulma, n.d., 10). *Stitching* should also be utilised to show transitions between sections, paragraphs, or sentences or to draw attention to previous or subsequent points otherwise in the essay.

While individual styles may vary, *style* is the last of the twelve items cited by (Gordon Harvey 2009), and should be 'exact and clear'; bring 'out main ideas and action of each sentence'; without being 'plain' and not flat.

4) IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE

Academic essays are in writing and are not generally part of extemporaneous communication between the writer and his audience.

In a contemporaneous interaction, the speaker has the benefit of making necessary adjustments depending on the 'real life' responses from his audience. He may clarify, expand, and may even correct mistakes made. He may also adjust the style and language used to accommodate the perceived reception and understanding of his audience.

Alas, this is not possible in a written piece, as the writer and audience are separated in terms of space (distance) and time.

There is, therefore, a greater burden placed on the writer to ensure that his message is communicated in the manner he intended and to the pleasure of his intended readers.

It is therefore important to first select the appropriate language, variety, and dialect; and in the case of academic essays, only formal languages and varieties, such as American or British varieties of the English language, and **not** a dialectal option (for example, ‘patois’), should be considered

The orthography (relevant rules of the written language) should then be complied with, such as spelling, grammar, and punctuation, and the variety (for example, Standard American English versus Standard British English) used should be consistent.

While there are extensive rules and books on punctuation, general rules relative to apostrophes, brackets, bullets/lists, colons, semicolons, commas, dashes, ellipses, and quotation marks should be revisited and employed. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16–23).

It must be noted that there is often disagreement with respect to the use of punctuation, and A R B Etherton writes that even ‘textbooks and dictionaries do not always agree on the use of a particular punctuation mark’ (Etherton 1990, 229).

5) REFERENCING STYLES

Referencing third-party sources and ideas is quintessential in academic writing and combats plagiarism discussed below.

Kate Turabian states that there are at least four reasons for referencing sources, namely: ‘to give credit’, ‘to reassure readers’, to show ‘the research tradition’ of your work, and ‘to help readers follow or extend your research’ (Turabian 2018, 141)

While there are multiple styles for referencing, utilising a **uniform** and **consistent** style is practical for the author, the reader, any reviewer, publisher, or other person seeking to read or review the work.

According to the University of Pittsburgh, a referencing (or citation) style “dictates the information necessary for a citation and how the information is ordered, as well as punctuation and other formatting” (University of Pittsburgh n.d.).

Some popular referencing styles include the APA (American Psychological Association) style, MLA (Modern Language Association) style, and Chicago/Turabian style. There are even specialist styles employed by particular institutions such as the World Health Organisation (WHO), which should be followed by “all staff members, as well as freelance writers and editors, who produce written information for WHO” (World Health Organization 2004, 1).

Admittedly, manual confirmation with reference styles may be tedious and time-consuming. Fortunately, however, there exists software tools to **assist** in this regard such as Zotero, mentioned further below.

6) PLAGIARISM

While “[p]lagiarism has never been and is not now a stable term—it has and will continue to change”, “there have been some consistent elements in our understanding and use of the concept.” (Grossberg 2008, 160)

Accordingly, it is generally acceptable that plagiarism is “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34).

Plagiarism is a challenge to integrity, which is important in academic writing.

Often, young or otherwise inexperienced writers may experience difficulty in this regard (Eberle 2013, 157), and therefore, it is important to understand what plagiarism is; and how to avoid it. Stefan Senders aptly posits, “[w]hen students plagiarize, are they ‘stealing’? Or are they merely demonstrating their lack of engagement with ‘the academic community’?” (Stefan n.d., 195)

The issue of plagiarism may be complicated and is broader than mere direct copying (Eberle 2013, 158).

Plagiarism may arise when you use words from a source without placing the same in quotation marks, even if you attempt to paraphrase or if you provide a footnote to the same (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 14).

"It is still plagiarism if you use an author’s key phrases or sentence structure in a way that implies they are your own, even if you cite the source” (Eberle 2013, 158).

The first step persons must take in avoiding plagiarism is to know the subject area of the paper and to not attempt to present something which they have not properly studied or are knowledgeable about. This is a mental step that will subvert any subconscious urge to plagiarise.

Secondly, people should ensure that they consider using third-party works and ideas only as necessary. Inundating your paper with lengthy quotations is strongly suggestive that you are not knowledgeable of your work (Cleenewerck and Gulma, n.d., 36). The more works and ideas you cite, the greater your analysis orientation and or reflection should be, the former being elements of the academic essay itself (Gordon 2009).

Thirdly, persons should be aware of items that need no citation, such as information deemed common knowledge (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 37).

Fourthly, those **relevant** quotations should be properly shown and referenced according to the appropriate referencing style (discussed above). Signal phrases may be employed as well, which is where a “quotation or paraphrase” is introduced “by using a verb and mentioning the author’s name” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 38).

As for paraphrasing, papers written in your own words may make the author appear better (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 36). However, one must not be capricious about paraphrasing, if done incorrectly, it may still violate plagiarism or may misrepresent the meaning of the original text intended to be referenced (Eberle 2013, 159).

Eberle (2013, 159) summarises the two ends of the paraphrasing/misrepresentation spectrum below: -

Plagiarism (implying or claiming the work of others as your own) results from either insufficient paraphrasing of the original text or from lack of an appropriate citation. Misrepresentation (inaccurately altering or attributing the work of others) results either from paraphrasing that alters the meaning of the original text or from providing a misplaced citation within the text.

Cleenewerck and Gulma provide for **four** central points in paraphrasing, namely that the words used must be your own without resembling the words or sentence structure of the original, the writing style be different from the original; the information presented ‘must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote’, and adequate references and citations must be used (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 36).

7) SOFTWARE AIDS

We live in the ‘Information Age’, and technology is very much a part of our lives.

Mondal et. al posit that ‘basic computer skills are essential for authors writing research papers and technology have become a fundamental part of the research and writing process’ (Mondal, Himel; Juhi, Ayesha; Dhanvijay, Anupkumar D.; Pinjar, Mohammed Jaffer; Mondal, Shaikat, n.d.).

Software tools have been developed to assist authors in writing academic essays. There are also tools that are available that expose plagiarism and allow for academic institutions to eradicate this ‘scourge’.

One must be aware that these tools should be utilised as such and be subservient to the author, who remains the ‘master’ in control at all times.

Unfortunately, some persons have reassigned their roles and, for example, utilised artificial intelligence to become the author of the work for which they seek to take credit. One popular example of this may be found in last year’s matter, where several lawyers in the state of New York submitted legal briefs generated by Artificial Intelligence without verifying the same, and the cases cited were discovered to be fictitious (Merken 2023). Such an example also exemplifies the need for there to be proper research and for sources

and evidence (elements of the essay mentioned above) to be properly evaluated and utilised.

One must also be conscious of the legality of the use of software tools, both in terms of the licensing requirements and terms of the particular software application, as well as any restrictions a particular academic institution may have in regard to the use of such application.

That being said, software tools include those that offer forms of cloud storage (such as Microsoft's One Drive), note-taking and synchronisation (such as Evernote or Samsung Note software), reference repositories and generation software (such as Zotero), and language-checking software (such as Grammarly).

Zotero allows users to input various sources and to have the same generated for easy insertion into their word processing software. This facilitates easier referencing and better adherence to styling formats.

Grammarly allows authors to identify and correct grammar and spelling errors. It also provides tools for evaluating plagiarism and text likely generated by artificial intelligence. It accordingly assists authors in providing a more appealing, linguistically accurate paper that also avoids plagiarism and generated text.

8) CONCLUSION

In sum, academic writing and essays fuel the academic and research community as well as elucidate readers at large. It, therefore, is meant to be of higher quality, not only in terms of delivery but also in terms of content and integrity.

It must, however, be disclaimed that essays should not be dull or boring and lack contribution to the subject matter, but rather should enlighten the audience and contribute to the topic in some form or fashion.

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